

EVALUATION OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHER PROSPECTIVE TRAINING MODEL BASED ON KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN INDONESIA

HERLINA USMAN^{1*}, GUSTI YARMI², USWATUN HASANAH³,
PRAYUNINGTYAS ANGER WARDHANI⁴, TAOFIK⁵ and OTTO FAJARIANTO⁶

^{1,2,3}Department of Primary Education, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

⁴Department of Primary Education, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

⁵Department of Primary Education, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Jakarta.

⁶Departemen of Education Technology, Faculty of Education, Universitas Negeri Malang.

Email: ¹herlina@unj.ac.id (*Corresponding Author), ²gyarmi@unj.ac.id, ³uswatunhasanah@unj.ac.id,

⁴prayuningtyasangger@unj.ac.id, ⁵taofik@unj.ac.id, ⁶otto.fajarianto.fip@um.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a training model for prospective elementary school teachers based on knowledge management system in improving their performance as professional teachers. The evaluation model used was the Kickpatrick model. The results showed that the teacher competency development training model can improve the performance of professional teachers. The ten competencies contained in the training model are supporting competencies to strengthen other teacher competencies. The results showed that in the pretest, the smallest average score was in the competency of ethical maturity and the largest average score was in the aspect of compelling communication. In the posttest, the average lowest score is found in the resilience aspect, while the average highest score is in the continuous learning aspect. This training model greatly contributes to supporting the four main competencies of teachers, namely pedagogical, personal, social, and professional.

Keywords: Elementary School Teacher; Training Model, Teacher Competencies.

1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of a new paradigm has made the teaching profession more open, meaning that those accepted as teachers do not necessarily have to be graduates of educational institutions. On the other hand, the opportunities for graduates of educational institutions have diminished as they must compete with graduates from non-educational institutions.

This condition further demands that universities continuously enhance their roles to produce professional teachers. In relation to the challenges and demands on the role of educational institutions, the development of the curriculum in these institutions has become very strategic.

Moreover, educational institutions are required to understand the development of teachers' professions as an effort to prepare graduates who possess academic qualifications and pedagogical, personal, social, and professional competencies as the Standards for Academic Qualifications and Competencies of Teachers (Gyampoh, 2020; Jannah et al., 2020; Renatovna & Renatovna, 2021). Especially in educational institutions that have a Primary School Teacher Education program, because a good primary education will serve as a solid foundation for students to continue to higher levels.

In addition to teachers needing to possess four competencies such as pedagogical, social, personal, and professional, teachers also have demands that must be mastered. These demands arise due to the development of science and technology and the era of the 21st century (Edwita et al., 2023; U. Hasanah et al., 2022; Lestari et al., 2024).

The 21st century is a very different era from previous centuries. The extraordinary development of knowledge in all fields during this century, especially in the field of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), which is highly advanced, makes the world feel smaller, as the sophistication of ICT technology allows various information from different corners of the world to be accessed instantly and quickly by anyone, anywhere, and personal communication can be done easily, cheaply, anytime and anywhere (Ariani, 2020; Bedir, 2019; Jiang, 2023).

These changes are increasingly felt, including in the world of education. Teachers today face challenges that are much greater than in previous eras. Teachers are confronted with students who are much more diverse, subject matter that is more complex and difficult, standards of learning processes, and also demands for higher student thinking abilities. Therefore, teachers who can compete are needed, not just in terms of intelligence but also creativity and action intelligence (hard skills - soft skills) (Azkia et al., 2025; Usman & Anwar, 2021).

The demands of the international world on the duties of teachers entering the 21st century are not light. Teachers are expected to be able to organize learning processes that are based on and implement the four pillars of learning recommended by the International Commission of UNESCO for education. This is based on the fact that education is an organized and continuous communication designed to foster learning activities in students.

Based on the description above, the researcher has developed a training model for prospective elementary school teachers to enhance their competencies so that they can adapt to the times. This model for developing the competencies of prospective elementary school teachers is based on the values of the Pancasila student profile, four teacher competencies, and four demands of teachers in the 21st century (Julia et al., 2022; Mtebe & Raphael, 2018; Sinagatullin, 2019).

This model is a discourse on developing ten competencies for prospective elementary school teachers, which consist of building positive working relationships; coaching; continuous learning; decision making; managing work; ethical maturity; mission/purpose; resilience; compelling communication; and valuing differences. This development model can serve as a foundation and strategic step in shaping the four core competencies of teachers in accordance with government regulations.

In addition, the impact of the realization of this model also supports the government in the formation of the Pancasila student profile for all students in Indonesia. Indirectly, the outcomes of this research can assist in the implementation of the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture for the years 2020-2024. Thus, this research is worthy of deeper examination as it has contributions and urgency for the advancement of education in Indonesia.

This model is packaged in a knowledge management system, and each competency is explained through the steps of ISMARIS (introduction, Self-Reflection, Material Exploration,

Assignments, Reflection, and Quiz). There are two reflections in this model aimed at ensuring that teachers always apply a reflective approach before proceeding and making decisions to act more wisely. In addition, there are other activities such as forum discussions, online learning features, and observations of the target respondents. This research aims to evaluate how effective the training model for prospective teachers that has been developed is. The research questions are:

1. What is the competency score of prospective teachers against the 10 competencies that have been trained?
2. What are the evaluation results of the elementary school teacher training model based knowledge management system according to the Kickpatrick model?

1.1 Training Model for Prospective Elementary School Teachers

This model is a new breakthrough for educational institutions that produce prospective teachers, especially elementary school teachers. A teacher is a person who is emulated and exemplified by their students. Therefore, the character of a teacher plays a crucial role in upholding professional teaching. This model is based on four teacher competencies, four demands of teachers in the 21st century, and the profile of Pancasila students. The theoretical framework is as follows:

Figure 1: Theory Framework

This model is a discourse on developing ten competencies for prospective elementary school teachers, which consist of building positive working relationships; coaching; continuous learning; decision making; managing work; ethical maturity; mission/purpose; resilience; compelling communication; and valuing differences.

This model is packaged in a knowledge management system. Knowledge management system is a digital-based tool used to help manage documents containing knowledge about general information.

The purpose of the knowledge management system is to provide a comprehensive understanding to parties in a unit regarding knowledge about learning. Thus, learning can be carried out optimally. The competency in the model is explained through the ISMARIS steps (introduction, Self-Reflection, Material Exploration, Assignments, Reflection, and Quiz). The explanations are as follows:

Home

The initial display contains an introduction and overview of this model, emphasizing character education and the competencies that will be studied. Below is its visual display:

Figure 2: Home Display

Introduction

When entering each competency, an introduction display will be presented. This display contains a general overview of the focus of that competency. Below is its visual display

Figure 3: Introduction Display for Each Competency

Self Reflection

This section contains self-reflection on the competencies being discussed. This activity aims to help teachers get used to reflecting on what they have done and to improve their performance to be even better. Here is the visual display:

Figure 4: Self Reflection Display

Material Exploration

In this section, prospective teachers are asked to review various reading sources related to the competencies. The reading materials can include articles, books, slides, videos, and posters. This activity aims for prospective teachers to express their opinions based on reasons and scientific sources. Here is the visual display

Figure 5: Display of Exploration material

Assignments

In this section, prospective teachers are asked to complete tasks relevant to the competencies. These tasks are carried out collaboratively and can take the form of case studies and team-based projects. The purpose of this activity is to enable prospective teachers to collaborate and find alternative solutions to every problem encountered. Here is the visual display:

Figure 6: Display of Assignments

Reflection

In this section, prospective teachers are asked to engage in reflective activities regarding the lessons and materials they have studied. This activity aims to help them become accustomed to analyzing the strengths, obstacles, and opportunities of the activities they have learned so that they can find a good formula to apply in future activities. The visual display is as follows:

Figure 6: Reflection Display

Quiz

In this section, the display will be integrated with the Quizziz application. Prospective teachers are asked to answer questions about the material they have studied. Here is the visual display:

Figure 7: Quiz display

This is a comprehensive overview of the training model for prospective teachers. This training model is activity-based, where each topic requires respondents to engage in realistic activities such as interviews, observations, and focus group discussions conducted to solve problems and determine alternative solutions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a training model for prospective elementary school teachers in improving their performance as professional teachers. The evaluation model used is the Kirkpatrick model. The explanation is as follows:

THE KIRKPATRICK MODEL

Figure 8: Kirkpatrick Model

In this study, the researcher conducted the evaluation up to the 'learning' stage. This is because the competency training model for prospective teachers is aimed at prospective teachers, meaning students of the elementary school teacher education program, so it cannot be measured from the 'behavior' and 'result' sides. The latter two stages can be assessed for prospective teachers who have become teachers, allowing the behavior and impact of the training to be measured. Therefore, to evaluate from the 'reaction' and 'learning' sides, several methods such as tests and focus group discussions (FGD) were conducted with several randomly selected respondents. The test is given after the prospective teachers complete the activities in the training model.

The test consists of essays related to the competency indicators that were trained. The test is designed as a one-group pretest-posttest, meaning the test is given before and after participating in the training. This aims to see the comparison and to what extent this training model contributes to the performance of prospective teachers. Meanwhile, FGD is a moderated discussion technique led by a researcher to discuss with a group of individuals who are purposefully selected and have similar backgrounds to express their personal experiences, beliefs, and attitudes. Additionally, FGD allows the researcher to understand the collective views and experiences as well as the meanings behind those views and experiences. In this study, four FGDs were conducted with teachers who had completed their training through this training model from September to November 2024.

It is suggested that a minimum of three to four FGDs is sufficient for research topics where complex issues are not investigated. Participants were selected considering specific features such as gender and semester level. The semester level is important because the college curriculum emphasizes the learning process in the 5th semester and beyond. In each FGD, balanced participation in terms of gender and semester level is ensured. Each focus group consists of 6-8 participants. The characteristics of the participants are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics of Participants

Characteristics	N
Gender	
Male	20
Female	19
Semester Level	
> Semester 5	27
< Semester 5	12
Total	39

A total of 39 respondents who are prospective teachers studying in the elementary school teacher education program in Padang participated. The discussion was facilitated and moderated by the researcher, who introduced several ideas to help the group have a natural and free conversation about their experiences and the impact of training in terms of whether there were changes in their practices. The discussion was also organized in such a way that participants had many opportunities to talk to each other, rather than answering the researcher's questions directly. This allowed the researcher to adopt the role of a facilitator rather than a

controller, so that the discussion occurred among participants rather than between participants and the researcher. The issues raised during the focus group discussion focused on the effectiveness of the training. Since all participants in the FGD had similar experiences, namely as prospective elementary school teachers and participants in the teacher competency development model training, the group found it easy to interact with one another. During the FGD, the researchers used a focused group schedule developed to observe the changes occurring among the teachers. The final version of the FGD schedule consists of four main sections/themes. The first section includes questions aimed at obtaining background information about the participants. The second section asks participants to reflect on the teaching and learning processes that occurred during the training in relation to their needs. The third section discusses how the training results are utilized by participants when teaching in their own classrooms. The fourth section focuses on the participants' overall evaluation of the process, particularly regarding the strengths and weaknesses of the model. The results of this FGD activity consist of three themes, namely discussing participants' overall evaluation of the training model, the strengths of the training model, and its weaknesses. For data analysis, content analysis is used. First, in the analysis process, the digitally recorded data is transcribed. The transcription is then coded by the researcher. After that, a number of related and similar codes are combined to obtain a more refined coding. Finally, the researcher looks for broader themes that incorporate these codes to understand the collected data and highlight the important messages conveyed by the participants.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results of Reaction

It was clearly stated in all FGDs that this training is very useful for both professional and personal development. Participants stated that working and socializing with their peers significantly contributes to their professional development and personal motivation. Participants welcomed efforts aimed at addressing common issues, building their experiences, sharing best practices, and discussing current issues under the guidance of the trainers. The explanation is as follows:

“I am very happy with the existence of this training because it provides the foundation to become a professional teacher.” (Respondent 5).

“I just realized that besides the 4 competencies of prospective teachers, there are also 10 characteristics that teachers must possess, and this is indeed very urgent.” (Respondent 16)

“This training has given me the experience that being a teacher must involve having ethical maturity. This is because teaching is a noble profession and must provide holistic learning to students, encompassing knowledge, morals, and ethics.” (Respondent 23)

This training model is very easy to follow; in addition to the important material, there are also assignments related to everyday life, making it more contextual. (Respondent 7).

I am happy to follow the flow of this training because it is very structured and easy to understand. In addition, there are also challenging quizzes. (Respondent 1)

I agree that this training is very beneficial for us prospective elementary school teachers. The ten competencies must be trained from an early age because they cannot emerge on their own. (Respondent 39).

Based on their opinions, almost 88% stated that this training model is very beneficial for teachers because these ten competencies will support the other four core competencies. They also expressed satisfaction with this training. Besides the exciting flow, the material is interesting, the quizzes are challenging, and there are tasks that are realistic to everyday life. The classification of reactions can be summarized as follows:

Figure 9: Reaction Themes

4. LEARNING TEST RESULTS

Based on the test results, it was found that there is a difference between the scores obtained in the post-test and the pre-test. Table 2 below briefly illustrates the fluctuation of scores in participants' performance by comparing the average scores they obtained in the pre-test (before the intervention plan) and the post-test (after the intervention). The table is as follows:

Table 2: Pre-test and Post-test Results

	Treatment	
	Pretest	Posttest
N	105	105
Mean	63,70	87,29
Standard Deviation	9,723	7,241
Standard Error Mean	972	724

Based on the calculations in table 1 above, it shows that the average score of the mean score before using the training model was 63.70 and after the treatment received an average score of 86.29. These results show that there is a descriptive difference in the average results of the teacher performance before and after following this training model. After the comparison results between the pretest and posttest were obtained, the next result was the correlation between the pretest and posttest as follows:

Table 3: Correlation Calculation Results

	N	Correlation	Sig.
Pretest	105	.629	.000
Posttest			

The table above shows that the correlation coefficient of students' pluralist attitude scores before and after is 0.629. The following is the Paired Sample correlation shown in table 3 below:

Table 4: Paired Sample Correlation Results

	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper
Pretest - Posttest	-22.590	8.711	.871	-20.279	-16.281	-19.294	119	.000

Table 3 above shows the average difference = -22.590, which means that the pluralist attitude score is higher after using the training model. Thus, there is a significant difference between the results before and after using the training model. The statistical score is $t = -19.294$ with $df = 99$ and a significant number, or $p\text{-value } 0.000 < 0.05$. The data obtained above shows that the application of the training model for the development of teacher competencies can improve professional teacher performance.

Table 5: Description of the Average Competence of Prospective Elementary School Teachers

No	Type of Competence	Pretest	Posttest
1	Building positive working relationship	62.11	87.20
2	coaching	60.16	79.17
3	continuous learning	67.58	88.28
4	decision making	63.28	86.20
5	managing work	60.16	82.42
6	ethical maturity	59.77	82.81
7	mission/purpose	67.19	83.98
8	resilience	62.5	66.41
9	compelling communication	75.78	79.69
10	value differences	63.28	83.59

Based on the table above, it shows that the competency scores of prospective elementary school teachers range from an average of 59.77 to 88.28. In the pretest, the lowest average score is found in the competency of *ethical maturity* and the highest average score is found in the aspect of *compelling communication*. In the posttest, the lowest average score is found in the aspect of resilience and the highest average score is found in the aspect of continuous learning.

Based on the findings above, it shows that the training model for developing teacher competencies can improve the professional performance of teachers. The ten competencies included in the training model are supporting competencies to strengthen other teacher competencies. The results show that in the pretest, the lowest average score is found in the competency of *ethical maturity* and the highest average score is found in the aspect of *compelling communication*. This result indicates that most of the audience already possesses the competency of Compelling communication. This ability is very important for prospective teachers, especially for elementary school teachers. A teacher should be able to create impactful communication. They have been able to maintain the audience's attention; use strong and engaging word choices and intonation to stimulate the thoughts and actions of others; use analogies and vivid illustrations to facilitate understanding; use visual aids if needed to enhance the impact of the message conveyed (Ahmed et al., 2018; H. Hasanah & Malik, 2020; U. Hasanah et al., 2021). In addition, they are also able to use language according to grammar and punctuation correctly and are able to use formats and terms appropriate to the topic and audience. Meanwhile, the lowest score is found in ethical maturity. This competency is indeed quite difficult because it relates to intrapersonal abilities. A prospective teacher must have integrity (Li et al., 2022; Pike et al., 2021). This attitude is inherent in moral, ethical, and professional standards, regulations, and existing policies, as well as maintaining commitment to promised actions (Aningsih et al., 2022; D'Olimpio, 2021; Pike et al., 2021). This competency is also important to be trained to prospective teachers because it concerns their self-esteem (Barbeau et al., 2022; Salavera et al., 2024; Sari et al., 2024; Scherr, 2022). A person with ethical maturity is able to act according to their values, standards, and self-confidence when facing pressure, ensuring that their words and actions are always consistent in different situations, and behaving wisely.

In the posttest, the average lowest score is found in the resilience aspect, while the average highest score is in the continuous learning aspect. In the resilience competency, teachers should maintain enthusiasm and focus on positive things when experiencing disappointment or rejection, viewing rejection as a challenge that requires greater effort. The highest score is found in continuous learning. The results indicate that most prospective teachers have already developed competencies in continuous learning. This competency directs teachers to be able to identify and participate in appropriate development and improvement activities; actively participate in various self-development and improvement activities in the most effective way (for example: taking notes, asking questions, critically analyzing information, always considering its application to work, completing assigned tasks) (Crawley & Nyahuye, 2022; Forsyth et al., 2022; Gebhard et al., 2022; Heiney et al., 2020; Roe, 2023; Usman et al., 2024). In addition to the competencies mentioned above, prospective teachers must be able to build good interpersonal relationships by making others feel valued, appreciated, and involved in

discussions (enhancing self-esteem, being empathetic, involving others, being open, and providing support). Thus, this training model for the competencies of prospective teachers significantly contributes to providing knowledge and strengthening the core competencies of teachers.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings in the field, it can be proven that the implementation of the training model for the competencies of prospective teachers is declared successful because it has a positive impact on all prospective teachers participating in this training. This is evidenced by the post-test results indicating that 90% of participants passed with scores above average. Furthermore, recommendations for future research include measuring behavior and impact once they have become professional teachers.

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Author Contributions Statement

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Herlina Usman	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Gusti Yarmi	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
Uswatun Hasanah	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
Prayuningtyas Angger Wardhani	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
Taofik	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	

C : Conceptualization

I : Investigation

Vi : Visualization

M : Methodology

R : Resources

Su : Supervision

So : Software

D : Data Curation

P : Project administration

Va : Validation

O : Writing - Original Draft

Fu : Funding acquisition

Fo : Formal analysis

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

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